

PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT OF USING FOLK GAMES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, the pedagogical content of the use of folk games in primary education is studied, and their special pedagogical value, freedom and voluntariness are analyzed in detail as the unique characteristics of games.

Key words: pedagogue, professional competence, classification, improvement, competence, competent approach, communicative, folk games.

INTRODUCTION. Going to the first school in primary grades is a very big event in the life of children. School life opens up a new world for children, the main activities of children change during the school period. From school age, the main activities and main tasks of children are studying. Children's learning activities require them to acquire new qualities and new skills. For reading activities, children need to have stable attention, a sharp mind, strong will, some thinking, good speech, will, and therefore independence, diligence, and creativity.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Specialists have been paying special attention to the problem of using folk games and didactic lessons to improve the effectiveness of education. Among the scientists of our republic are M.Abdullajonova, B.R.Adizov, A.Y.Bobomurodova, O.Jamoldinova, B.Ziyomuhamedov, G.Ibragimova, R.Ishmuamedov, U.I.Mahkamov, M.H.Mahmudov, O.Musurmonova, D.Sharipova, Sh.Sharipov, N.M.Egamberdiyeva. this was reflected in his works.

From foreign scientists A. Yolanda, N. Nicotera, A. Christopher, L. Botcheva, J. Shih, L. C. Huffman, L. D. Breeman, van Lier, Theo Wubbels, R. Sears, J. L. Spilt, E. Vervoort, A. Koenen, F. Clemente, A. Amutio, L. Gonzalez's studies have explored the possibilities of games in the formation of social skills and basic competencies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Games are of particular importance in the organization of educational activities in primary education. In order for games and educational activities based on games to provide an opportunity to achieve the expected effectiveness, it is necessary to correctly define what tasks can be solved in the process of their implementation. The organization of such games should be started from the elementary grades as much as possible. Educators

and psychologists say that if the student is not interested, the acquired knowledge will not have a positive effect on his emotions and will not serve his intellectual development [3]. Also, in the process of mastering this knowledge, students cannot establish friendly communication with their classmates.

The game is a means of knowledge, creativity, and spiritual-intellectual development of students. With the help of the game, a new world opens up to students. It is impossible to fully develop students without using the game. In the process of the game, students master the system of mutual relations, enter into cooperation, develop and form as individuals. The game has special value as a complex social-cultural and didactic phenomenon, and has been the object of many philosophical-cultural, pedagogical-psychological studies. Games play a special role in establishing communication between students. Its complexity is determined by the uniqueness of game activity in the pedagogical process. Their special pedagogical value, freedom and voluntariness are recognized as the unique features of games. Games are practically oriented and have special pedagogical value as they serve to obtain a guaranteed result.

The game teaches the student to think, to be resourceful, to think logically. On this basis, it helps to form one's own "I". It also creates the need to learn to know and initiates new changes. The game opens up new opportunities to communicate with the outside world. The game is a universal concept and has its own concepts and terms in philosophy, pedagogy, psychology, historical theory, and art. In general, in the scientific language, the game is also used in the sense of dramaturgy, spectacles, holidays, festivals, carnivals, and artistic creativity.

In the big encyclopedic dictionary, it is shown that the game is not only a productive activity, but its motive is manifested not in the results, but rather in the process itself. This process brings pleasure to the players, and the audience gets pleasure from it. For this reason, it plays an important role in the effective course of the educational process, it helps in the development of the student as a person, in increasing his interest in working in life, studying and learning, and in psychological preparation. In general, the concept of game has a wide meaning, and it is difficult to express it with one rule. Often, the answer to this question is, "Why does everyone play?" a broader answer can be obtained only when the question is asked [4].

In his time, the Russian scientist P.F. Lesgaft suggested dividing games into simple and complex. He, in turn, mainly distinguished the games included in them, depending on the types of actions.

Simple games include: a) running games; b) throwing games.

Complex games include: a) running games; b) throwing games; c) games related to fighting elements.

It is known from history that in the ancient system of education, games were widely used as a means of personal formation. Pedagogists understand the educational importance of the game very cleverly. They believed that it is possible to find out the behavior of children during the game in relation to any situation, to identify their negative and positive qualities more easily, and to apply effective measures to eliminate inappropriate behavior. Therefore, even in those times, the issue of choosing suitable games for children, taking into account their age characteristics, was raised. It is considered necessary to engage in activities and games according to the child's age. Educators are tasked with choosing such games.

The Greek philosopher Plato recommended learning science through games. He believed that children show their abilities better in the game. Also, Plato says: "Teach people pleasant subjects not by force, but through games, and then you can better see who is inclined to what" [2]. Aristotle, one of the ancient philosophers, said that it is necessary to use games for children to spend their free time in a meaningful way, that games are fun and help to have fun [1]. Therefore, games have a great place in the development of pedagogical methods.

According to Usman Karaboyev, the national games of the Uzbek people and the action games within it have a history of several thousand years, and they have their own content in social life. That is, the games that appeared in the era of social systems have been improving in terms of content and essence, and have the following directions, that is:

1. Games at wedding ceremonies and holidays.
2. Action games played in the family, neighborhood, streets.
3. Play alone and in pairs.

Action games in this direction are divided into the following types in terms of content:

- games representing work and social life;
- games played in or reflecting the seasons;
- games related to the life of animals and birds.

Currently, the main task of folk games is to ensure the education of students in accordance with the requirements of our society, to develop communication skills in them, to form the knowledge, skills and abilities, characteristics and qualities of creative people.

Uzbek folk games are a product of collective creativity of the Uzbek people, created and preserved by the general public. Games have been perfected for centuries as a necessary element of the life and social life of many generations of the Uzbek people and performed various social tasks at each historical stage of development. Uzbek folk games embody the creative power of history, material and spiritual wealth, and reflect the historical experience of knowing and mastering the surrounding reality. Uzbek folk games are practical in nature. The uniqueness of the folk artistic culture and its national characteristics are clearly visible in them.

Uzbek folk games were created in ancient times before our era. According to the study of the traditional life of the Uzbek people, historically "Herdsman", "Lame wolf and sheep", "Goats and shepherds", "White camel", "Bo' A number of Uzbek folk games such as ri keldi" originated. Among our people, very interesting dances on the theme of animals and birds, such as "Kaptaro'yini", "Chagaalak", "Yumronkaziq", "Ot oyini" are popular. Also, among the Uzbeks, "Trumpet, Trumpet", "Nina, thread and wind", "Tapir-topur kairagoch", "Pumpkin planting", "Battle of roosters", "Rooster and chicken", " Games such as "Run, my child, the bird came", "White poplar-blue poplar" were also popular.

The social life, labor activity and lifestyle of the people are reflected in their own forms in the national games of the people. They show very rich emotions and experiences, loving and protecting their Motherland.

According to the content, purpose-logic and direction of the children's folklore games, which have passed through the experimental tests again and again and have reached us intact and perfect in the thousand-year historical path of our people, they are divided into the following types. can be

1. Seasonal children's folklore games: folklore games played in the early spring, summer, and winter seasons.

2. Ceremonial children's folklore games: pictures, customs, rituals, games played on traditional holidays.

3. Children's folklore games related to work: "Plowing the earth, plowing", "Planting crops", "Melon-melon", "Pruning apricots", "Melon bunch", "Mulberry knocking", " Apricot drying", "Pomegranate picking", "Strawberry harvest", "Yanchik", "Khosh-hosh", "Churey-churey", "Khushey-khushey", "Cow milked", " Bringing a camel back", "Horse watering" and others.

4. Children's folklore games on family and household topics: "Guest-guest", "Bride-dropping", "Bride-groom", "Mother-child", "Cooking", "House furnishing",

"Kog "Irgakh game", "Bread bread", "Couple", "Alla-alla", "Crib decoration", "Beshikka Belash" and others.

5. Children's folklore games with physical movement: "Quvlashmachok", "Zyrak", "Goose-geese", "Chasing the ball", "Bunny-bunny", "Olarsan-a", "Epchil" rabbit, "Toptash", "Count", "Chiqadak", "White bone". "Run", "Zuv-zuv", "White poplar, blue poplar", "Donkey rode", "Ball", "Think", "Don't listen", "Get to me", "Sokka", "Lanka", "Fighting", "Cockfight", "Climbing the pole", "Climbing the mountain", "Bring the toys", "Standing under the water", "Capricorn", "Chasing", "Swimming", "Long Jump", "Tug of War", "Horseplay", "The Girl Who Chased", "Racing", "Target Shooting", "Fencing", "Archery", "Stone" raise" and others.

6. Logical children's folklore games: quick sayings, riddles, counting, sayings, questions and answers, guess, recall, guessing and others.

7. Ball folklore games related to animals and natural phenomena.

8. Fun folklore games for children.

9. Music games.

The division of Uzbek children's folklore games into such types is relative. After all, if some of them start to be performed as soon as winter ends and spring comes, it can continue actively throughout the year. At the same time, a game played in summer can be played in winter, or vice versa, a game played in winter can be played in summer.

CONCLUSION. If games are used correctly in schools, the effectiveness of education will increase and students' interest in science will increase. Game-independent education means mastering the subject, section, theme, and concept. Play is a very emotional activity, which is why it requires seriousness in the educational work of children and young people. With the growth and development of the child, the content of the game changes, if the game activity is simple in the early stages, then it gradually becomes richer and more sophisticated. Through games, students move on to mastering other types of work and learning resources. As a result, their life imagination expands and their creative activity grows.

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